

An Assessment of Three Leaders at the National, Regional and Continental Level in Relation to the Contingency Theory of Leadership

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Abstract:- Contingency Leadership Theory guides the application of Contingency (Situational) Leadership approach which emphasizes the style a leader applies in the situation in which he operates. This paper assessed the styles of Sheikh Mohammed Al-Maktoum, President Paul Kagame and President Olusegun Obasanjo as global, regional and national leaders respectively in the context of Contingency Leadership Theory. The common denominator found among the three leaders was that they were all at one time or the other military men and this to a far extent shaped their authoritarian leadership styles. On the basis of this, the study concluded that the dictatorial, autocratic, despotic and benevolent democratic styles applied by the three leaders accounted for the remarkable successes they recorded in the course of exercising their assigned mandates.

Keywords: *Contingency Leadership Theory, Contingency Leadership, Dictator, Autocrat, Despot, Benevolent Democrat.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The verb leadership has been around for nearly 200 years, while the basic term leader dates back to A.D. 1300. (Stogdill, 1974). Leadership is often defined by the researcher's perspective and the phenomenon's most interesting elements. Stogdill (1974, p259) stated that "there are almost as many definitions of leadership as there are people who have sought to define the concept." Since Stogdill's remark, more definitions have poured in.

According to Stogdill's research, leadership is defined by traits, behaviors, influences, interaction patterns, role linkages, and occupation of a position. Some writers define leadership as a form of power dynamic in which members of one group believe they have the right to dictate to members of another group. Koryak et al (2015) describe leadership as the ability to lead by example, communicate goals effectively, and mobilize resources to achieve rapid outcomes.

The preceding points indicated that leadership centers around the traits enunciated in Stodgill's study as well as those enhanced by Koryak. Leadership nowadays is defined by important traits such as influence, power, authority, and factors that characterize the circumstance in which a leader finds himself. In this context, Group 2 defines leadership as a social impact displayed by a person in power utilizing authority - conferred on him by law, tradition, or personal attributes - to maximize the efforts of followers towards achieving a desired goal. An excellent leader is the driving force behind any successful private or public organization, according to Freeman & Siegfried (2015).

Theories are the primary means through which Social Scientists attempt to explain and predict the behavior of many phenomena in the real world. As a result, a wide range of theoretical frameworks in the social sciences are used to examine various leadership styles. Trait (large man) theories, behavioral theories and contingency theories are a few examples of theories. Three strategic leaders at the national, regional, and continental levels are identified and evaluated in this work using the theory of contingency leadership.

II. CONTINGENCY THEORY OF LEADERSHIP

In his article titled "A Contingency Model of Leadership Effectiveness," Fred Edward Fiedler (1964) laid the groundwork for the Contingency Theory of Leadership. The "Contingency Theory of Leader Effectiveness" was the name of the theory (House & Aditya, 1997). The Contingency Leadership is a leadership method that focuses on how a leader's personality (traits) and behavior interact with situational variables to form his leadership style. Based on research findings, task-motivated and relationship-motivated leadership styles were identified as the two most prevalent.

Motivated by tasks, whereas motivated by relationships, refers to the interpersonal relationships that one has in one's life.

The Least Preferred Coworker Scale was developed by Fiedler to measure task and relationship-motivated leadership styles (LPC scale). Relationship-motivated leaders outrank task-motivated leaders on this scale (Northouse, 2007, p.114). Contingency leadership models are used to assess whether a leader's style is task or relationship oriented, and if the circumstances match that type to maximize performance (House & Aditya, 1997). For one thing, according to Contingency Theory of Leadership, a person's leadership effectiveness may vary depending on the scenario. Because of this, it is necessary to examine each situation to determine whether a particular leadership style is effective or not (Indeed Career Guide, 2020).

III. RELEVANCE OF CONTINGENCY THEORY OF LEADERSHIP

Because it is based on actual study, contingency theory has lasted for decades as a credible and trustworthy approach to effective leadership. Rather of focusing only one optimum form of leadership (e.g., the trait approach), the theory now emphasizes the relevance of a leader's personal style as well as the demands of many contexts. Most of Fiedler's claims about the contingency theory have been confirmed by researchers who have followed in his footsteps.

Theory is a framework for explaining concepts in the subject of research in order to predict the actual behavior of a phenomenon being investigated in the real world. Theories. When it comes to the study of leadership, contingency theory has proven its worth in the field of social science because of its ability to anticipate the type of leadership strategy and style that will be most successful in a given situation. According to Contingency Theory, leadership styles like relational and task-motivated styles are linked to Contingency Leadership as a form of leadership technique.

IV. CONTINGENCY THEORY OF LEADERSHIP APPLIED TO GLOBAL, REGIONAL AND NATIONAL LEADERSHIPS

In corporate organizations, relational and task motivated styles are frequently used in the context of contingency leadership approaches. The imperatives required for leaders to function efficiently in the sphere of political governance go beyond the relational and task motivated leadership styles that are common among managers in corporate companies. While carrying out their assigned mandates at the global, regional, and national levels, strategic level political leaders require additional characteristics such as dictatorial, autocratic, despotic, and democratic styles to supplement their Contingency Leadership type.

Accordingly, the purpose of this study is to use the Contingency Theory of Leadership as an analytical tool to discuss global, regional, and national leaders such as Sheikh Mohammed Bin Rashid Al-Maktoum of the United Arab Emirates, Paul Kagame of Rwanda, and Olusegun Obasanjo of Nigeria, who served as President of Nigeria from 1999 to 2007.

V. SHEIKH MOHAMMED BIN RASHID AL-MAKTOUM AS A GLOBAL LEADER

➤ *Background*

Sheikh Mohammed bin Rashid Al Maktoum, the former Crown Prince of Dubai, was born in 1949. He was Sheikh Saeed's third son and the youngest of his siblings. Sheikh Mohammed grew up in his family's home in the Al Shindagha district, where he attended school. When Sheikh Mohammed's grandfather, Sheikh Rashid, was the ruler of Dubai, he presided over regular informal meetings (Majlis), when the most respected people of the city came to address concerns of a variety of different kinds. Although Sheikh Mohammed was still a child at the time, he was a regular participant in these gatherings.

Sheikh Mohammed has been taking individual studies in the Arabic language and Islamic knowledge since he was a child. In 1955, he enrolled at the Al Ahmadiya School, where he completed his elementary education (Mayo et al. 4). He went to the university to study Arabic Grammar, English, mathematics, geography, and history. He graduated from Dubai Secondary School in 1965 and then traveled to the United Kingdom in 1966. During his time in the United Kingdom, he attended the Bell Educational Trust's English Language School. The following year, Sheikh Mohammed enrolled at Mons Officer Cadet School, where he underwent military training (Sahyouni, 2019).

Education in the United Kingdom, which is a cosmopolitan setting, as well as the military training he acquired while there prepared Sheikh Mohammed for a leadership position. In 1969, he was appointed as the commander of the Dubai Police Force, and on December 2, 1971, he was named as the country's Minister of Defense. Sheikh Mohammed was appointed as Dubai's crown prince in 1995, and on January 4, 2006, he was formally installed as the Emirate's ruler. On 5 January 2006, he was named as Vice President of the United Arab Emirates, and on 11 February 2006, he was appointed as Prime Minister of the United Arab Emirates (UAE) (Wikipedia, 2016).

➤ *The Situation in Dubai at the time Bin Rashid became Ruler*

Sheikh Mohammed bin Rashid Al Maktoum succeeded his elder brother Sheikh Maktoum bin Rashid Al Maktoum as Ruler of Dubai in 2006, following the death of his elder brother. Since the death of his father in 1990, Sheik Maktoum has been the ruler of Dubai. Dubai, one of the Kingdoms in the United Arab Emirates federation of seven Gulf states, has been transformed into one of the region's economic hubs, and he is widely seen as the driving force behind this development (VOA, 2009). While Sheikh Maktoum was the ruler of Dubai, his younger brother Sheikh Mohammed was the driving force behind the majority of the city's economic growth projects during his time as the ruler.

Sheikh Mohammed had already begun overseeing the construction of a massive business and leisure park in Dubai, which would eventually be able to accommodate approximately 10 million people, at a time when Gulf oil

reserves had declined to the point where oil contributed only about 6 percent of the emirate's gross domestic product. Since becoming ruler, Sheikh Maktoum bin Rashid Al Maktoum has made it possible for members of his family to exercise complete command and control over all key developments in Dubai. Members of the royal family hold all of the state's highest-ranking positions.

➤ *Sheikh Mohammed Bin Rashid Al Maktoum's Style of Leadership*

The relational and task motivated styles of leadership have been identified as complements to Contingency Leadership approach especially in corporate organizations. However, political leaders require additional attributes such as dictatorial, autocratic, despotic and democratic styles to complement the type of leadership approach exhibited by a leader. On the basis of the prevailing situation in 2006 when Sheikh Mohammed Bin Rashid Al Maktoum assumed the leadership of Dubai following the death of his elder brother, he fits to be described as a Contingency (Situational) Leader. Mohammed Bin Rashid's late elder brother's leadership style was authoritarian, dictatorial and autocratic in the sense that he ensured that his family's hold on political and economic power in Dubai was absolute.

Mohammed Bin Rashid's elder brother's leadership style was therefore the template he followed when he became the ruler of Dubai. An authoritarian or dictatorial leader issues orders and directives and is clearly in control of affairs of the organization he leads. Mohammed Bin Rashid considered the situation he found himself after his brother's death an emergency situation in which quick decisions are necessary in line with the principles of chain of command. His military training in UK came in handy on account of some of the dictatorial tendencies he exhibits in the course of taking decisions.

Mohammed Bin Rashid was however not an absolute dictator or autocrat in the sense that he demonstrates respect for others, acknowledges inputs by others in decision making situations, recognises accomplishments and provides clear expectations and resources to meet them (Jenkinson, 2018). On the whole, Mohammed Bin Rashid is a benevolent authoritarian and dictatorial leader. What sets him apart from absolute dictators is that he has a bold vision for his country which serves as a source of inspiration and influence to his followers. Additionally, Bin Rashid's leads Dubai as if he is leading a family, in this regard, he is known as "the CEO" of Dubai because he makes his followers to feel that they are working for a big family (Sayhyouni, 2019).

➤ *Achievements of Mohammed Bin Rashid Al-Maktoum*

According to documented evidence, Mohammad Bin Rashid Al-Maktoum is a Contingency (Situational) Leader with a leadership style that is authoritarian yet benevolently dictatorial in nature. In defining his vision and working toward the achievement of his strategic goals, Mohammed Bin Rashid Al-Maktoum is an excellent leader who successfully combines type and style of leadership. Mohammed Bin Rashid Al-Maktoum has been hailed as a spectacular worldwide leader on several occasions since

assuming the role of ruler of Dubai. This has been based on his numerous accomplishments since assuming the position of ruler.

Among Mohammed Bin Rashid Al-most Maktoum's prominent accomplishments has been his contribution to economic growth and development in the UAE. Despite the fact that Dubai was founded as an oil-producing country, oil exports today account for only around 4.5 percent of the country's gross domestic product (GDP), with commerce and non-oil sectors accounting for the majority of the country's GDP. Over the course of his reign, Mohammed Bin Rashid Al-Maktoum has transformed Dubai's economy from one that is heavily reliant on oil to one in which the tourism industry contributes significantly to the country's economic prosperity.

Because of the leadership style that Mohammed Bin Rashid Al-Maktoum brought to bear on the government of Dubai, infrastructural development has accelerated under his watch. As a result, Dubai's economy has grown to become one of the most important in the Middle East area. Dubai's GDP per capita has increased dramatically over the previous decade, owing to the fact that the country's economy is no longer reliant on oil extraction. Dubai's sectors are numerous, with the construction industry, real estate, tourism, finance, and wholesale and retail trade among the most prominent.

The real estate industry is one area in which Mohammed Bin Rashid Al-accomplishments Maktoum's are visible. The profitability of real estate investments in Dubai is one of the highest in the world, making it a desirable place to invest. A significant portion of Dubai's budget is allocated to real estate development, with transactions in the industry being carried out by investors from more than 140 countries. The standard of living in Dubai is really high. In this regard, education at all levels is provided free of charge, and the government emphasizes the necessity of encouraging adult men and women to participate in literacy programs. The average monthly income of a citizen is approximately US \$4000, and the average monthly income of a certified specialist begins at approximately US \$10,000 ("UAE Economy: Labour Pains," section 3).

Specifically in the field of labor relations, Mohammed Bin Rashid Al-Maktoum demonstrated a distinctive leadership style by altering perceptions and working cultures in Dubai, and indeed throughout the entire United Arab Emirate Region, and bringing them into line with world-class practices and standards. He abolished the government's clock-in and clock-out system and replaced it with what he referred to as a "citizen's conscience," thereby transferring responsibility to the individual employee as well as giving them the trust and power to help transform Dubai into a better and more sustainable state in the long term. According to Mohammed Bin Rashid Al-Maktoum, the love that people have for their homes should be the driving force and guiding concept that motivates them to go to work each day (Abu Naama, 2016).

Another accomplishment attributed to Mohammed Bin Rashid Al-Maktoum was the establishment of a foolproof system to ensure that anybody residing in Dubai received the correct treatment and service from employees and other government officials. Mystery shoppers were deployed to all outlets in Dubai, including stores, ministries, and other origins, to assess the quality of the services supplied. This was done across the entire spectrum of government services. In order to maintain complete anonymity, these mystery shoppers came from a diverse range of socioeconomic origins as well as different age groups. Mohammed Bin Rashid Al-Maktoum discovered techniques to test his teams in the most natural setting possible in order to acquire an accurate report on the performance of each department as a result of this discovery. This strategy was deemed to be a great test for Dubai's huge government staff, and it was implemented (Department of Economic Development, 2017). The majority of Mohammed Bin Rashid Al-Maktoum's accomplishments were recognized around the world, earning him the title of global leader in the process.

VI. PRESIDENT PAUL KAGAME OF RWANDA - A REFLECTION OF A REGIONAL LEADER

➤ *Background*

Paul Kagame was born on the 23rd of October, 1957, in the Rwandan capital of Kigali. During his tenure as leader of the Rwanda Patriotic Front (RPF), he defeated Hutu extremist troops, bringing the 1994 Rwanda genocide to an end. In the year 2000, he was elected President of the Republic of Rwanda. The Rwandan president grew raised as an exile in Uganda, where his parents took him as a small kid when Hutu violence against Tutsis erupted in 1959, during the period leading up to the country's independence from Belgium. In Uganda, he attended Makerere University in Kampala before joining the forces of Yoweri Museveni, who overthrew the country's president Milton Obote in 1986 with the help of the Ugandan military. Kagame rose to the position of Museveni's chief of intelligence, earning a reputation for incorruptibility and severity by implementing a severe code of conduct that was uncompromising.

➤ *Rwanda's political situation at the time Kagame was elected president*

The existence of ethnic tension in Rwanda has been a constant since the Belgian colonial period, as there have been continual tensions between the Hutu majority and the Tutsi minority since that time. Rwanda gained independence from Belgium in 1962, and the Hutus quickly seized control, using the Tutsis as scapegoats for every issue that occurred throughout the following decades.

Rwandan President Juvenal Habyarimana, a Hutu, was assassinated on April 6, 1994, when his plane was shot down over Kigali, the capital city. Kagame, who was then the leader of a Tutsi rebel group in Uganda, and some of his close associates were accused of carrying out the rocket attack, which Kagame categorically denied. Following Habyarimana's death, the situation escalated to the level of a national emergency, with the presidential guard launching a campaign of retaliation almost immediately. Leaders of the

political opposition were assassinated, and the slaughter of Tutsis and moderate Hutus began almost soon after their deaths. The Rwandan Patriotic Front (RPF), a group of around 10,000-14,000 soldiers, was formed in response to the genocide and was directed against Hutu forces responsible for the massacre.

The Rwandan People's Front (RPF) took Kigali in July 1994, resulting in the collapse of the government and the declaration of a truce by the RPF. Following the RPF's conquest of Kigali, an estimated two million Hutus fled to the Democratic Republic of the Congo. Following that, a multi-ethnic government was established, with a Hutu, Pasteur Bizimungu, serving as president and Mr Kagame serving as his vice president. However, the two later became estranged, and Bizimungu was sentenced to prison on charges of inciting ethnic violence. After that, the status remained unchanged until an election was conducted in 2003. Kagame ran for president of Rwanda in 2003 under the guise of being a Rwandan rather than a Tutsi, and he attempted to downplay the presence of ethnic tensions in the country. In the country's first multi-party presidential election, he won by a landslide, becoming him the country's first multi-party president. On September 12th, 2003, he was sworn into office, effectively bringing the nine-year transitional administration to an end. His presidency was characterized by a strong emphasis on strengthening national unity as well as the economics of the country.

➤ *President Kagame's Style of Leadership*

Having received military training in Uganda, Tanzania, and the United States, President Kagame is an astute military strategist. He had been a refugee in Uganda since infancy, and during the course of his time there, he rose to become a founding member of Ugandan President Yoweri Museveni's rebel army, which was established in 1979. Kagame was in charge of the organization's intelligence section, which assisted Museveni in gaining power in 1986. (BBC News, 2017). Having grown up as a rebel and a military officer, Kagame's attitude on life and leadership style as a politician were impacted by his experiences as both.

Kagame took over as Rwanda's leader with little or no experience in democratic leadership. The fact that he spent much of his early life under the mentoring of Yoweri Museveni, who himself was a rebel commander before becoming President of Uganda, did not lend credence to the notion that he was a democratic figure. Consequently, Kagame's leadership style was predetermined to be that of a brutal autocratic, despotic, dictatorial, and authoritarian leader. A Contingency Leader was the sort of leadership he demonstrated as President of Rwanda because of the circumstances that existed at the time he assumed the position of President of the country.

Since taking office, President Paul Kagame has never presented himself as a kindly autocratic leader. Based on how his dictatorship has violently suppressed the opposition and murdered some of his most prominent critics, Kagame's hold on power appears to be unbreakable. Following the constitutional reform passed in 2015, Kagame is allowed to

run for a total of three additional terms, allowing him to remain in office until 2034 under the current administration. Additionally, Kagame adheres to the Machiavellian style of leadership, in which the leader maintains power via deception and pretense while acting immorally and deceiving others (Nwoko, 1988).

➤ *Kagame's Achievements as a Regional Leader*

Getting Kagame to the next level as a regional leader will require him to first demonstrate his abilities at the national level. As early as his first year in office, Kagame began actively devising strategies for achieving national development goals. The constitutional process was started, and he also sought the counsel of specialists from growing countries such as China, Singapore, and Thailand. Following these meetings, and shortly after taking the presidency, Kagame presented "Vision 2020," an ambitious national development vision that has garnered widespread support. The primary goal of the program was to bring the Rwandan people together and to transform the country from one of extreme poverty to one of middle income.

Many leadership literatures have demonstrated that dictatorial, despotic, and autocratic type leaders, whether benevolent or not, who exhibit Contingency are more likely to succeed. Leadership characteristics typically produce outcomes more quickly than democratic leadership features. Consequently, decisions are made quickly, and projects are completed at the pace specified by the organization's leadership. Paul Kagame is included in this group of world-class leaders. When Kagame's RPF came to power in 2003, Rwanda was in ruins on all fronts: economically, socially, and politically. Rwanda has made significant strides forward in the last fifteen years under Kagame's leadership.

The impressive achievements of President Kagame can be seen mostly in the domain of infrastructural development. Rwanda's economic prosperity has been fueled in great part by the efficient infrastructure that has been built under Kagame's leadership. Rwanda's road network has significantly improved, and the country is gradually opening up to the rest of the world with the development of a national airline and the construction of an international airport worth \$800 million (£605 million). Rwanda's standing as a commercial hub would be enhanced by the construction of a conference center, which will cost at least \$300 million, according to President Paul Kagame. With a per-capital gross domestic output of \$1592 in 2003, Rwanda's economy has developed at a rapid pace under Kagame's leadership, compared to a per-capital gross domestic product of \$567 in 2000. Between 2004 and 2010, the annual rate of increase averaged 8 percent every year. Liberalization of the economy, privatization of state-owned companies, the reduction of bureaucratic bottlenecks in business, and the transformation of the country from an agricultural to a knowledge-based economy are the cornerstones of his economic policy.

Youth education in Rwanda has also been identified as a high priority by President Kagame, with the sector receiving a 17 percent allocation from the country's annual budget. His administration provides free education in state-run schools for

a total of twelve years: six years in primary school and six years in secondary school, with the final year of secondary school being free. During the same period, the number of universities increased from one in 1994 to 29 in 2010, and the proportion of undergraduates increased from 4 percent in 2008 to 7 percent the following year. According to Kagame's strategy of preserving close ties with English-speaking countries, he applied for membership in the Commonwealth of Nations, which he eventually received in 2009. Rwanda was the second country to join the Commonwealth after Mozambique, and it was the only one to do so without having any colonial ties to the British Empire.

From the 28th of January 2008 to the 10th of February, 2019, Kagame served as the African Union's chairperson. As chair of the African Union, Kagame advocated for the establishment of the Single African Air Transport Market (SAATM) and the establishment of the African Continental Free Trade Area (ACFTA). The proposed ACFTA was signed on March 12th, 2018 by 44 of the 55 member countries of the African Union. He departed office in February 2009, with the CFT having already been ratified by 19 of the 22 countries that were required for it to become fully effective. With his effective performance at the continental level of the African Union, Kagame has earned the right to be considered a regional leader.

VII. PRESIDENT OLUSEGUN OBASANJO AS A NATIONAL LEADER

➤ *Background*

Olusegun Obasanjo was born on March 5, 1937, in the city of Abeokuta, Nigeria. Former President Olusegun Obasanjo attended Baptist Boys' High School in Abeokuta, southwest Nigeria, and went on to become a teacher there. Because he couldn't afford college, he enlisted in the army in 1958 and got officer training in the United Kingdom. Obasanjo ascended through the ranks at a rapid pace. His commando division was stationed in the Biafran front in South Eastern Nigeria during the Biafran war (1967–1970), and he was appointed to that position throughout the conflict. In January 1970, Biafran forces surrendered, bringing the conflict to a close.

Following the successful transition program of General Abdulsalami Abubakar, Chief Olusegun Obasanjo was elected as Nigeria's second elected executive president on May 29, 1999. This handover effectively signaled the beginning of the fourth republic of Nigeria (Olurode and Anifowoshe, 2004). As president, Obasanjo has presided over Nigeria for eight years, making it the longest stretch of civilian government in the country's modern political history. Between 1999 and 2007, Obasanjo implemented a wide range of socio-economic and political initiatives during his tenure as President of the Republic of Nigeria.

➤ *The Situation in Nigeria at the time Obasanjo became President*

Obasanjo became president at a period when Nigeria was just emerging from the global community's pariah position due to past military regime misdeeds, particularly

General Sani Abacha's. At the national level, Nigeria was tense as religious, ethnic, and political fault lines erupted, endangering the country's corporate survival. After Abacha's death in June 1998, General Abdulsalami Abubakar became Nigeria's military ruler.

Following the successful holding of the elections that were part of General Abdulsalami's transition program, Obasanjo took over as civilian executive President on May 29, 1999. Assuming the presidency, Obasanjo immediately set about restoring Nigeria's socio-economic stability and re-establishing diplomatic ties with the world community.

➤ *President Obasanjo's Leadership Style*

Presidency Obasanjo began with political pressures inherited from General Abdulsalami's regime, which had much improved the socio-political inadequacies inherited from the Abacha junta's misrule. Obasanjo's initial leadership style was formed by the socio-political milieu he found himself in. With his leadership background, Obasanjo took tough but far-reaching measures to help stabilize Nigeria's political situation. First, military officers who had political positions under previous military administrations had to quit immediately. Obasanjo's first significant administrative decision showed that he will be an authoritarian leader in a democratic society. Events proved it. Obasanjo needed to move quickly to speed up Nigeria's socio-economic and political growth. Only benevolent dictatorial and autocratic leadership styles, rather than relational and task-oriented leadership styles, could achieve this. Obasanjo wasn't a normal democrat. He believed in rapid decision making, even if it meant dismissing the legislative branch of government as a hindrance to government functions. Obasanjo tried to encircle the National Assembly by deposing three Senate Presidents and a House Speaker. These actions portrayed Obasanjo as an autocratic leader impatient for results.

➤ *Achievements of President Obasanjo on account of his Leadership Style*

Obasanjo's policies were to widen and strengthen democracy, develop political institutions to assure its long-term survival, and remedy Nigeria's inherent federalism flaws. For example, zoning of political positions mirrored the federal character and power-sharing principles. It assigned significant political roles inside the federation to the six geopolitical zones to achieve power balance.

The Obasanjo government launched the National, State, and Local Economic Empowerment Development Strategies (LEEDS). They were the administration's main social-economic reform measures from 2003 to 2007. (Rustad, 2008). Corruption, self-sufficiency, poverty, privatization, and deregulation were all targets of NEEDS. More notably, the administration repaid a large amount of Nigeria's Paris Club debt in 2006. (Chiakwelu, 2012).

During the military governments that preceded Obasanjo's, corruption was rampant. Obasanjo established the ICPC in 2000 and the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) in 2004 to combat high levels of corruption (Nwankwu, 2008). Obasanjo's achievements,

especially the EFCC, according to Okoosi-Simbine (2011). Tafa Balogun, a former Inspector General of Police, Patricia Etteh, a former House Speaker, Adolphus Wabara, a former Senate President, and even Obasanjo's Vice-President Atiku Abubakar were investigated or prosecuted for government corruption. In June 2000, Obasanjo's government established the Niger Delta Development Commission (NDDC). The Commission was established to advise the federal government on how to develop the Niger Delta economically (Falola and Geneva, 2009). Other notable accomplishments of President Obasanjo can be attributed to his efficient leadership style, which he used to manage Nigeria as a civilian President. Obasanjo's accomplishments make him a worthy national leader.

VIII. ADVANTAGES AND SHORTCOMING OF CONTINGENCY LEADERSHIP THEORY

The Contingency Leadership Theory is easy to employ in assessing leaders, especially those with strategic leadership responsibilities. The theory's main tenet is that a leader with the correct style knows it. All a leader needs to do is assess the scenario and apply appropriate leadership style. The Contingency Leadership Theory also has an intuitive appeal in that leaders can alter management methods fast to match the current dynamics. Conversely, Contingency Leadership Theory fails to explain why certain leaders are effective in some contexts but not others. Because the Least Preferred Co-Worker Scale does not correlate well with other established leadership measures, the hypothesis is criticized. Finally, Contingency Leadership fails to adequately describe how to deal with a leader/situation mismatch (Northouse, 2007, p.118-120).

IX. CONCLUSION

Contingency Leadership Theory says that the concept stresses both the leader's attributes and the context in which the leader operates. The Contingency Leadership Theory identified Task-motivated and Relationship-motivated as the two prevalent leadership types. These two styles were judged to be most suitable in business environments. To fulfill their mandates, strategic level political leaders need other traits beyond dictatorial, autocratic, despotic, and democratic approaches.

According to this study, the Contingency Theory of Leadership reasonably explains how Contingency Leadership type connects to relational and task-oriented leadership styles, and extreme approaches such as dictatorial, autocratic, despotic, and democratic styles usually dictated by tough political requirements at strategic levels. This study used the Contingency Theory of Leadership to analyze Sheikh Mohammed Bin Rashid Al-Maktoum, Paul Kagame, President of Rwanda, and Olusegun Obasanjo, former President of Nigeria.

The study concluded that the three leaders highlighted had many accomplishments due to their leadership styles. The three leaders had one thing in common: they were all former military men, and this affected their leadership approaches.

These leaders were all autocratic in style and lacked democratic leadership experience. Unlike Bin Rashid and Obasanjo, Kagame was not a good autocrat. Kagame was a brutal despot driven by the ethnic division in Rwanda exacerbated by the 1994 genocide.

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